

Evidence for Steric Enhancement of Resonance in 2-Alkylanisoles from ^{13}C NMR T_1 Relaxation Times of Methoxy-carbons and from Atomic Charges on Methoxy-oxygens

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Steric effects in aromatic methyl ethers were studied by the application of ^{13}C nmr spectroscopy¹ and PRDDO-MO calculations². A careful examination of the data obtained in the above study reveals that the methoxy group in 2-alkylanisoles has a greater electron-releasing power than that in anisole, but such an examination was not made. The detection of this steric enhancement of resonance³ (SER) in 2-alkylanisoles requires measurements of high sophistication, as pointed out by us in a recent communication⁴. The measurements and calculations made by Jardon *et al.*¹ fulfil this requirement and they are used in the present communication to furnish additional evidence for SER in 2-alkylanisoles.

The major mechanism of relaxation for carbons bonded to protons is through the ^{13}C -H dipole-dipole mechanism¹. An increase in the rate of reorientation of ^{13}C nuclei will result in less efficient relaxation and therefore longer T_1 values. Jardon *et al.* found from T_1 measurements that carbons of methoxy groups flanked by two *ortho*-alkyl groups show a larger T_1 than those having only one *ortho*-alkyl group. The methoxy group of the latter lies in the plane of the ring away from the *ortho*-substituent⁵. In this conformation, rotation around the O-CH₃ bond is coupled weakly to the adjacent ring hydrogen⁶, resulting in lower T_1 values. An alternative explanation¹ is that with two adjacent *ortho*-groups, rotation around the O-CH₃ bond is unhindered because

the methoxy group is away from the plane of the benzene ring (2a-d) and longer T_1 values result (Table 1).

1

- a R = H
- b R = CH₃
- c R = C₂H₅
- d R = CH(CH₃)₂
- e R = C(CH₃)₃

2

- a R₁ = R₂ = CH₃
- b R₁ = R₂ = C₂H₅
- c R₁ = R₂ = CH(CH₃)₂
- d R₁ = R₂ = C(CH₃)₃

TABLE 1— T_1 RELAXATION TIMES OF METHOXY CARBON

Anisole	T_1 Relaxation time
1a	6.5
b	5.0
c	4.6
d	4.0
e	5.1
2a	11.1
b	9.2
c	7.0
d	8.2

In anisole (**1a**) the methoxy group is more free to rotate around O-C_{Ar} bond than the methoxy groups in *o*-alkylanisoles (**1b-e**) and thus a relatively longer T_1 is observed. In *o*-alkylanisoles (**1b-e**) the methoxy group executes restricted rotation in the plane of the benzene ring and its ability to conjugate with the benzene ring increases⁴. The enhanced resonance in **1b-e** compared with the resonance in anisole (**1a**) is reflected in lower T_1 values.

Table 2 data show the variation of excess negative charge on the oxygen atom as well as the *ortho* and *para* carbon atoms for coplanar conformation of methoxy group with the benzene ring in the case of **1a** and **1b** and for the preferred conformation (the angle between the plane of the methoxy group and the plane of the benzene ring being 90°) in the case of **2a**. The methoxy oxygen is less negative in **1b** than in **1a** indicating enhanced resonance of the methoxy group compared with its resonance in anisole.

TABLE 2-ATOMIC CHARGES

Anisole	Atomic charge		
	O	C-4	C-6
1a	-0.288	-0.068	-0.086
b	-0.286	-0.069	-0.087
2a	-0.304	-0.059	-0.036

The C-6 and C-4 of **1b** are more negative than those of **1a** pointing to the same fact. There being steric inhibition of resonance in **2a**, the oxygen becomes more negative and the electron density at the *ortho* and *para* ring positions is less in **2a** than in **1b**.

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